

THEORETICAL BASICS OF USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract: *Abstract: The current stage of human development is characterized by the rapid development of globalization processes. If we look at globalization from an economic point of view, it means the establishment and development of a system of economic relations covering the entire space of the world economy.*

Therefore, in the conditions of globalization, the problem of forming an active person who can independently make decisions, set and implement goals, and consciously evaluate his own activities is becoming urgent.

Ensuring the organization of the educational process on the basis of developing technologies is one of the most urgent tasks today. Now, the teacher should not limit himself to imparting knowledge and forming practical skills, but should teach students to learn independently, search and make decisions.

Key words: *education, training, pedagogue, pedagogical technology, knowledge, skills, theory, spirituality, culture, psychological education, differentiated approach.*

Аннотация: *Современный этап развития человечества характеризуется бурным развитием глобализационных процессов. Если рассматривать глобализацию с экономической точки зрения, то она означает становление и развитие системы экономических отношений, охватывающей все пространство мирового хозяйства.*

Поэтому в условиях глобализации становится актуальной проблема формирования активной личности, способной самостоятельно принимать решения, ставить и реализовывать цели, сознательно оценивать собственную деятельность.

Обеспечение организации образовательного процесса на основе развивающихся технологий является сегодня одной из наиболее актуальных задач. Теперь учитель должен не ограничиваться передачей знаний и формированием практических навыков, а должен научить учащихся самостоятельно учиться, искать и принимать решения.

Ключевые слова: *образование, подготовка, педагог, педагогическая технология, знания, умения, теория, духовность, культура, психологическое образование, дифференцированный подход.*

Annotatsiya: *Insoniyat taraqqiyotining hozirgi bosqichi globallashuv jarayonlarining jadal rivojlanishi bilan tavsiflanadi. Agar globallashuvga iqtisodiy nuqtai nazardan qarajak, bu jahon xo'jaligining butun makonini qamrab oluvchi iqtisodiy munosabatlar tizimining o'rnatilishi va rivojlanishini anglatadi.*

Binobarin, globallashuv sharoitida mustaqil qarorlar qabul qila oladigan, maqsad qo'ya oladigan va amalga oshira oladigan, o'z faoliyatini ongli ravishda baholay oladigan faol shaxsni shakllantirish muammosi dolzarb bo'lib bormoqda.

Rivojlanayotgan texnologiyalar asosida ta'lim jarayonini tashkil etishni ta'minlash bugungi kunning eng dolzarb vazifalaridan biridir. Endilikda o'qituvchi

faqat bilim berish, amaliy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish bilan cheklanib qolmay, o'quvchilarni mustaqil bilim olishga, izlanishga, qaror qabul qilishga o'rgatishi kerak.

Tayanch so'zlar: ta'lim, tarbiya, pedagog, pedagogik texnologiya, bilim, malaka, nazariya, ma'naviyat, madaniyat, psixologik tarbiya, tabaqalashtirilgan yondashuv.

Organizing the educational process on the basis of developing technologies requires great skill from the pedagogue. Developing technologies require the teacher not only to impart knowledge to students, to form practical skills in them, but also to develop their personality. This is achieved through mutual trust, cooperation and lively communication between the teacher and the learner. Developmental technologies require a different approach to the training process. The teacher has to change his attitude towards the student and science.

It is necessary for the pedagogue to respect the learner's personality, give up the commanding method of communication, encourage him, emphasize the usefulness of his work. The goal is not to form pre-defined characteristics in the student, but to allow him to realize himself and show his identity.

Traditional education is based on compulsion, the organization of teaching on the basis of strictness, in which the learners hardly work independently and their initiatives are suppressed. In traditional education, the student's educational activity does not have a creative character.

In order for us to use our professional skills, not only to control the knowledge and skills of learners, but also to help with our competent efforts to eliminate the difficulties that may arise in knowing and applying the knowledge, skills and competences, we should direct their activity to diagnosis.

Developing technologies, by their essence, imply the full development of all participants of the educational process. This is not only a differentiated approach to education taking into account the readiness of the learner, his abilities and opportunities, but also taking into account the psychological, professional and personal characteristics and abilities of the learner.

Our Republic pays great attention to developing technologies and its implementation in secondary special, vocational education and training of independent and free-thinking young specialists. Also, in addition to organizing the educational process at a high level, the main goal is to prepare students for professions according to their interests, desires and needs. Today, it is important for

vocational colleges to train junior specialists based on the demands and needs of the market economy, to form knowledge, skills and abilities of students based on the requirements of the state educational standards in the fields of training, and to develop the ability to work independently in the future. For this, it is necessary to create a scientifically based mechanism for the organization, management and quality control of the educational process in vocational colleges based on a new approach and modern methods.

During the development of educational technologies, we implement developmental educational technologies.

As can be seen from the above drawing, the realization of the goal and the achievement of a guaranteed result depend on the cooperative activity of both the teacher and the student, the goal they set, the chosen content, method, form, tool, i.e. technology. It is up to the teacher and the student to choose the technology for the student to achieve the goal, because the main goal of both sides is clear: to achieve the result, in which the technology used is chosen depending on the student's level of knowledge, the nature of the group, the conditions, for example, the result to achieve it, maybe it is necessary to work with a computer, maybe you need a film, handouts, drawings and posters, various literature, information technology, it depends on the teacher and the student.

Because the person is one of the main components of the "National Personnel Training Program"; it is also the main subject and object of the personnel training system, the goal of the education system, and remains its authoritative subject. A number of studies have studied the possibilities of using developing technologies in vocational education and their practical application.

In particular, in the works of Q. Tolipov, the essence and content of modern pedagogical technologies, especially the possibilities of using modular and problem-based teaching technologies in the educational process, are highlighted.

I.A. In his scientific work, Allayorov developed didactic foundations of active teaching and scientific methodical recommendations for student activation were reflected. N.N. Azizkhodzhaeva's literature describes pedagogical technologies and their role and importance in the educational process. B.L. Farberman's works reveal new pedagogical technologies and their role and importance in the educational process. It is worth noting that in most researches and scientific pedagogical works, only the teaching technology is covered theoretically.

The features of production should be reflected in the content of special subjects, the student should be able to apply theoretical knowledge in practice. Vocational college students should have sufficient knowledge and skills in the methods of activity related to a special subject.

Conclusion

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teacher and the student. It is necessary for the teacher to design the future lesson process in order to be able to see each lesson as a whole and imagine it. It is very important for the teacher to draw up a technological map of the upcoming lesson. Because the technological map of the lesson is created based on the nature of the subject, the subject being taught for each subject, and the capabilities and needs of the students.

REFERENCES.

1. Etiquette of official and unofficial meeting T. "Adolat" 1992.
2. Saidnazarov F, Saidnazarov I, Education, manners, and consequences T. "Uzbekistan"
3. Gudratov T. Basics of speech culture T. "Teacher" 1993
4. E. Goziev "Psychology of communication" Tashkent 1990.
5. Navoi A. "Mahbub ul-Qulub" work. Volume 15.
6. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". T.: Uzbekistan 1991.
7. Avloni A. "Turkish Gulistan or morality". Tashkent: Teacher, 1992.160 p.
8. Bekmirzayev N. "Fundamentals of the art of public speaking" T.: New century. – 2008. -200 p
9. Kaikovus. "Nightmare". Tashkent: Istiklal. – 1994. 173 pages.